

DATA CLINICS

INFORMATION SHEET FOR PARTNERS

Concept:

- Real-world ethical challenges and decision-making processes.
- Led by academics from TUM, they provide practical advice on navigating questions around responsible data practices, data governance, ethical guidelines, or policies.

The goal is to empower participants with actionable insights to handle complex issues like privacy, discrimination, transparency, and accountability, and thus foster wider cultures of ethical data work.

What are Data Clinics?

Data clinics are an interactive collaboration and teaching format designed to bridge theory and practice in the realm of data governance and ethics. Clinics bring together partners and practitioners with Masters students from the Technical University of Munich to work together in a structured way on real-world ethical challenges and decision-making processes. They run as part of the teaching programme at the Chair for Philosophy and History of Science and Technology at the Technical University of Munich.

Who are we?

We are a team of international researchers led by the Chair for Philosophy and History of Science and Technology, Prof. Dr. Sabina Leonelli, and part of the Ethical Data Initiative (EDI), a non-partisan platform fostering open discussions on data ethics. We focus on equity and engagement across different domains of data work for public interest, informed by philosophical, historical, and social studies of science.

What are our requirements?

Time Requirements: The Data Clinics can come in two formats, as a semester-long course or as part of an intensive “project” week. A representative from your institute or organization should dedicate around four to five hours in total to engage with our students. This may include, for instance, two hours at the beginning of the clinic to explain your background, how you work with data, and the challenges you face; one hour for feedback and exchange at an interim stage; and two hours for final feedback and discussion.

Material Requirements: You need to be able to disclose sufficient detail of your data practices and challenges to provide students (and us) with concrete material to work with and analyse effectively. For example, you might demonstrate your data infrastructure, share samples of relevant data, and outline concrete issues you are facing.

What can we offer you?

- High-level expert advice and mentoring tailored to the specific conditions of your data ecosystem and challenges. (Note that we do not provide legal advice.)
- The opportunity for expert-led, structured co-learning and engagement, working with smart and motivated students at Masters level from the TUM.
- We are more than happy to think about specific ways in which the Data Clinics can support and intersect with your work, while also providing an enriching co-learning experience for students.

Contact

TUM Lehrstuhl: Prof. Sabina Leonelli (sabina.leonelli@tum.de)